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A generic approach in tackling the Yang-Mills Theory’s existence and mass gap problem – Conditions found for which the mass gap do not exist in different gauge theories

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ABSTRACT. The Yang-Mills Theory’s existence and mass gap problem is one of the unsolved problems in mathematics and mathematical physics. It is proposed by the physicists Chen Ning Yang and Robert Mills in 1953. Although the academical literature expects the mass gap to exist in non-abelian gauge theories (e.g. quantum chromodynamics resp. QCD) in any dimensions less or equal than 4, until this day, no unconditional and generic proof valid for all dimensions, circumstances and use cases could be delivered for the mass gap existence even in non-abelian gauge theories like quantum chromodynamics resp. QCD. In our work, we firstly build our main particle model for both abelian gauge theories (e.g. QED) and especially non-abelian gauge theories like QCD (non-pure QCD with matter fields & quarks and pure QCD without quark particles). Then we apply the energy-momentum relation to our main particle models and finally we are able to disprove the existence of mass gap in both abelian and non-abelian gauge theories like QED and non-pure & pure QCD through discovering a set of counter examples and conditions for which the mass gap existence is not feasible, because the relationship between mass of the massive particle in non-vacuum state and the minimum decrease of initial momentum of the original particle in vacuum derived from the energy-momentum relation formula would always be violated under these conditions and circumstances.

1. Introduction

The Yang-Mills Theory’s existence and mass gap problem is one of the unsolved problems in mathematics and mathematical physics. It is proposed by the physicists Chen Ning Yang and Robert Mills in the 1950s of the last century. The main focus of our research work is to try to validate whether there exist a mass gap in the Yang Mills theory that is a quantum field theory including quantum chromodynamics (QCD) and in broader sense also quantum electrodynamiccis (QED). While QCD mainly models the interactions of between quarks and gluon particles (and especially in pure QCD also the massive glueballs besides the massless gluons), the key focus of QED is to describe the interactions of charged particles (like electrons) in a electromagnetic field and light particles (photons).

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In the next chapter 2, we will build our main particle model first using the quantum electrodynamics (QED) framework (chapter 2.1) and then we utilize the quantum chromodynamics (QCD) with matter fields & quark particles (chapter 2.2) and lastly the pure QCD without quark particles (chapter 2.3) for our new assessment of the mass gap existence in the Yang-Mills theory.

Although the academical literature expects that the mass gap should exist in non-abelian gauge theories (which especially includes quantum chromodynamics resp. QCD) in any dimensions less or equal than 4¹, up to this day, no unconditional resp. generic proof (valid for all dimensions, circumstances and use cases) could be delivered for the mass gap existence even in those non-abelian gauge theories like quantum chromodynamics resp. QCD².

In this research paper, the main focus would be to show under which generic conditions and circumstances the mass gap could possibly exist (and if there exist irregularities or counter examples to the mass gap existence) for use cases in quantum electrodynamics (QED), quantum chromodynamics (QCD) with matter fields & quarks and finally in pure quantum chromodynamics resp. QCD without quark particles³.

1 cf. i.a. Farakos, K., Koutsoumbas, G. & Sarantakos, S. (1987) and Modal (2023)

2 Modal (2023) tried a new geometrical approach and proved the mass gap existence under some specific conditions (e.g. positive sign of corresponding regularized Bakry-Émery Ricci curvature) in the non-abelian renormalized Yang-Mills theory (which is a renormalized resp. extended version of the non-abelian Yang-Mills theory) and restricting the domain of analysis to less than 5 real coordinates dimensions resp. especially to the 4th and 3rd dimensional real coordinates space.

3 For completeness reasons and for better demonstrating our analytical approach with our newly built main particle model, we will try to find conditions of mass gap existence in quantum electrodynamics (QED) which unlike non-abelian gauge theories like quantum chromodynamics (with quarks or pure QCD without quarks) is not of main interest of the academic community but it (QED, an abelian gauge theory) is still included in the Yang-Mills quantum field theory in the broader sense.

2. Main model set up & Energy-momentum relation

In this chapter, we will firstly craft and set up our main particle model in quantum electrodynamics (QED), quantum chromodynamics (QCD) with quarks and without quarks (pure QCD) for our analysis and reassessment of the validity of the mass gap existence problem within the Yang-Mills theory. Then we will mainly use the Energy-momentum relation equation for performing our analysis of the changes and dynamics in the main particle model.

2.1 Set up of our main particle model in QED and the corresponding Energy-Momentum relation

In this subchapter 2.1 we will firstly build our main particle model in quantum electrodynamics (QED) including photons and electrons, before we present some important equations and formulas (like e.g. the energy-momentum relation equation applied to our QED particle model framework) for better mathematically analyze the conditions for mass gap existence in Yang-Mills theory.

2.1.1 Set up of our main particle model in QED

The starting point for building our main particle model in quantum electrodynamics (QED) is a single (massless) photon⁴ travelling resp. propagating through the empty space (which is in the vacuum state) and within an electromagnetic field, with positive (external) electromagnetic force F_{ext} .

Then another single electron (with small mass > 0) at rest is added to the system with 1 single photon within the electromagnetic field.

⁴ Depending on the situation, photons are called particles, waves or excitations. The latter expression is especially used in quantum field theory like in QED resp. quantum electrodynamics.

The photon then collides with the other added electron (initially at rest) which causes the photon to lose momentum while (part of or all) this lost momentum is transferred to the electron at rest.

1) If all of the lost momentum of photon is transferred to the electron at rest (which means that non of the transferred momentum is balanced out resp. nullified by the external electromagnetic forces), then a mass gap could potentially exist (we will show this reasoning in more detail with a concrete numerical example later on)

2) Only if not all of it is transferred to the electron at rest (e.g. because a part of the transferred momentum to the electron is nullified by the external electromagnetic forces), then mass gap could not exist (we will show this reasoning in more detail with a concrete numerical example later on as well)

2.1.2 Energy-momentum relation equation in QED

The energy-momentum relation is a relativistic formula that connects total energy resp. relativistic energy of one or multiple bodies and particles to their rest mass (if it exists) and its momentum. The energy-momentum relation for a single particle is defined as follows:

$$E_{TotalSingleParticle}^2 = (pc)^2 + (mc^2)^2 \rightarrow E_{Total} = \pm \sqrt{((pc)^2 + (mc^2)^2)} \rightarrow E_{Total} = \sqrt{((pc)^2 + (mc^2)^2)} \quad (1)$$

For a system including multiple resp. N particles in total, the energy-momentum relation is defined as follows:

$$E_{all\ particles}^{Total} = \sum_{i=1}^N E_i^{Total} = \sum_{i=1}^N \sqrt{((p_i c)^2 + (m_i c^2)^2)} \quad (2)$$

Thus the squared equation form for all N particles could be written down like this:

$$\left(E_{all\ particles}^{Total}\right)^2 = \sum_{i=1}^N \left(E_i^{Total}\right)^2 = \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\left(p_i c\right)^2 + \left(m_i c^2\right)^2\right) \quad (3)$$

And for a 2 particle system ($N = 2$) the total energy levels consisting of kinetic energy (i.a. depending on its momentum) and rest energy (i.a. depending on its mass) is defined as follows:

$$E_{2\text{ particles}}^{Total} = \sqrt{\left((p_1 c)^2 + (m_1 c^2)^2\right)} + \sqrt{\left((p_2 c)^2 + (m_2 c^2)^2\right)} \quad (4)$$

Thus the squared equation form for a system of 2 particles could be written down like this:

$$\left(E_{2\text{ particles}}^{Total}\right)^2 = \left((p_1 c)^2 + (m_1 c^2)^2\right) + \left((p_2 c)^2 + (m_2 c^2)^2\right) \quad (5)$$

When applying the settings of our main particle model consisting of 1 single photon and 1 electron (e.g. residing in an electromagnetic field) the total energy level is defined as follows:

$$E_{\text{photon+electron}}^{Total} = \sqrt{\left((p_{\text{photon}} c)^2 + (m_{\text{photon}} c^2)^2\right)} + \sqrt{\left((p_{\text{electron}} c)^2 + (m_{\text{electron}} c^2)^2\right)} \quad (6)$$

Therefore the squared equation form for a system of 2 particles (1 photon + 1 electron) could be written down like this:

$$\left(E_{\text{photon+electron}}^{Total}\right)^2 = \left((p_{\text{photon}} c)^2 + (m_{\text{photon}} c^2)^2\right) + \left((p_{\text{electron}} c)^2 + (m_{\text{electron}} c^2)^2\right) = \left(E_{\text{non-vacuum}}^{Total}\right)^2 \quad (7)$$

So the squared energy levels of a single photon (e.g. in vacuum state) is define with this formula:

$$\left(E_{\text{photon}}^{Total}\right)^2 = (p_{\text{photon}} c)^2 + (m_{\text{photon}} c^2)^2 = \left(E_{\text{vacuum}}^{Total}\right)^2 \quad (8)$$

Now the most important part of our work is the mass gap definition which is the energy difference between the total energy level in non-vacuum and the initial vacuum state:

$$\Delta\left(E^{Total}\right) = \left(E_{\text{non-vacuum}}^{Total}\right) - \left(E_{\text{vacuum}}^{Total}\right) \quad (9)$$

For convenience reasons⁵ we could also look at the difference between non-vacuum and the vacuum state of the squared total energy levels, because if a mass energy gap does exist between squared energy levels, then it would also exist in normal non-squared energy levels between the vacuum and non-vacuum state:

$$\Delta\left(\left(E^{Total}\right)^2\right)=\left(E_{non-vacuum}^{Total}\right)^2-\left(E_{vacuum}^{Total}\right)^2 \quad (10)$$

Just as elaborated before in chapter 2.1, in order to check the existence of mass gap in Yang-Mills theory resp. quantum field theory (which includes both quantum chromodynamics (QCD) and quantum electrodynamics (QED) ⁶), we will set up our main particle model that includes

- a) 1 photon in vacuum state and
- b) 1 photon + 1 electron in non-vacuum state.

When applying the settings of our main particle model consisting of 1 single photon and 1 electron (e.g. residing in an electromagnetic field) the total energy level is defined as follows as we could already see in the formula (6) above:

$$E_{photon+electron}^{Total}=\sqrt{\left(\left(p_{photon}c\right)^2+\left(m_{photon}c^2\right)^2\right)}+\sqrt{\left(\left(p_{electron}c\right)^2+\left(m_{electron}c^2\right)^2\right)}$$

And the formula (9) from above tells us that the mass gap resp. total energy difference between vacuum and non-vacuum state would only be positive (>0), if the total energy levels in non-vacuum levels is strictly bigger than the total energy in the vacuum:

$$\Delta\left(E^{Total}\right)=\left(E_{non-vacuum}^{Total}\right)-\left(E_{vacuum}^{Total}\right)$$

5 The squared version of the mass gap definition is more convenient, because later on we will encounter squared roots in e.g. the non-squared energy-momentum formula (6) resp. the non-squared version of the mass gap resp. delta energy formula (9) which could not be negative (if we do not want to deal with complex numbers which is not the main focus of our research paper).

6 While quantum chromodynamics (QCD) mainly deals with particle interactions between quarks and gluons, quantum electrodynamics (QED) describes the interactions between charged particles within an electromagnetic field (like for example the interactions between photons and electrons). The key focus of the research work would be on the latter, the quantum electrodynamics.

Thus if the initial kinetic energy (of the single photon) of the vacuum state reduces more (or exactly the same) compared to the increase of rest energy (of the electron particle) in non-vacuum state when switching from vacuum state to non-vacuum state (where massful particles like electrons exist besides e.g. the massless photons, in our case 1 photon + 1 electron), then the mass gap do not exist (in the Yang-Mills theory). These use cases and situation could potentially occur in specific circumstances, e.g. when a moving photon collides with the single resting electron within a given electromagnetic field (including external forces like for example electromagnetic forces). We will analyze this use case in more detail and with concrete numerical examples in the next chapter 3.

2.2 Set up of our main particle model in QCD with quarks and the corresponding Energy-Momentum relation

In this subchapter 2.2 we will firstly build our main particle model in quantum chromodynamics (QCD) including quarks particles, before present some important equations and formulas (like e.g. the energy-momentum relation equation) for better mathematically analyze the conditions for mass gap existence in Yang-Mills theory.

2.2.1 Set up of our main particle model in QCD with quarks

Our main particle model in quantum chromodynamics (QCD) including quarks particles is a single (massless) gluon travelling resp. propagating through the empty space (that is in the vacuum state) and within an color field consisting of only gluons, with positive (external) force F_{ext} . The single massless gluon could exist within the QCD framework (incl. quarks particles), because we assume that very high energy and temperature levels like e.g. that the gluons are residing in the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) of CERN in Geneva, Switzerland.

Then another single meson (e.g. a quark-antiquark pair with small mass > 0) at rest is added to the system with 1 single gluon within the color field consisting of only gluons (which is only possible in a high energy resp. high temperature environment).

The gluon then collides with the other added meson (initially at rest) which causes the gluon to lose momentum while (part of or all) its lost momentum is transferred to the meson at rest.

1) Just like in the example of quantum electrodynamics (QED) above, if all of the lost momentum of photon is transferred to the electron at rest (which means that non of the transferred momentum is balanced out resp. nullified by the external forces emitted from the color field), then a mass gap could potentially exist (we will show this reasoning in more detail with a concrete numerical example later on).

2) Only if not all of it is transferred to the meson at rest (e.g. because a part of the transferred momentum to the meson is nullified by the external forces emitted from the color field), then mass gap could not exist (we will show this reasoning in more detail with a concrete numerical example later on as well) ⁷.

2.2.2 Energy-momentum relation equation in QCD with quarks

Let us recall from formula (4) of chapter 2.1 that in the 2 particle system (N = 2) the total energy levels consisting of kinetic energy (i.a. depending on its momentum) and rest energy (i.a. depending on its mass) is defined as follows:

$$E_{2\text{ particles}}^{\text{Total}} = \sqrt{\left((p_1 c)^2 + (m_1 c^2)^2\right)} + \sqrt{\left((p_2 c)^2 + (m_2 c^2)^2\right)}$$

Thus the squared equation form for a system of 2 particles could be written down like this, just as formula (5) has already shown us:

$$\left(E_{2\text{ particles}}^{\text{Total}}\right)^2 = \left((p_1 c)^2 + (m_1 c^2)^2\right) + \left((p_2 c)^2 + (m_2 c^2)^2\right)$$

⁷ It should be mentioned that unlike in the QED example from chapter 2.1 it is not possible on QCD (with or without quarks particles) it is not possible to completely balance out resp. nullify the transferred momentum from massless particle (gluon) to the massive particle (e.g. meson) by external forces of a quantum field (which is a color field solely consisting of gluons).

When applying the settings of our main particle model consisting of 1 single massless gluon and 1 massive meson (e.g. residing in a color field) the total energy level is defined as follows:

$$E_{gluon+meson}^{Total} = \sqrt{\left((p_{gluon} c)^2 + (m_{gluon} c^2)^2\right)} + \sqrt{\left((p_{meson} c)^2 + (m_{meson} c^2)^2\right)} \quad (11)$$

Therefore the squared equation form for a system of 2 particles (1 gluon + 1 meson) could be written down like this:

$$\left(E_{gluon+meson}^{Total}\right)^2 = \left((p_{gluon} c)^2 + (m_{gluon} c^2)^2\right) + \left((p_{meson} c)^2 + (m_{meson} c^2)^2\right) = \left(E_{non-vacuum}^{Total}\right)^2 \quad (12)$$

Thus the squared energy levels of a single gluon (e.g. in vacuum state) that exist on in high energy environment is define with this formula:

$$\left(E_{gluon}^{Total}\right)^2 = (p_{gluon} c)^2 + (m_{gluon} c^2)^2 = \left(E_{vacuum}^{Total}\right)^2 \quad (13)$$

Now we need to use the formula (9) from previous chapter 2.1 which is the mass gap definition (that is the most important formula in our work) which is the energy difference between the total energy level in non-vacuum and the initial vacuum state:

$$\Delta\left(E^{Total}\right) = \left(E_{non-vacuum}^{Total}\right) - \left(E_{vacuum}^{Total}\right)$$

For convenience reasons⁸ we could also look at the difference between non-vacuum and the vacuum state of the squared total energy levels (which is the formula (10) from chapter 2.1) because if a mass energy gap does exist between squared energy levels, then it would also exist in normal non-squared energy levels between the vacuum and non-vacuum state:

$$\Delta\left(\left(E^{Total}\right)^2\right) = \left(E_{non-vacuum}^{Total}\right)^2 - \left(E_{vacuum}^{Total}\right)^2$$

⁸ Just as elaborated in chapter 2.1, the squared version of the mass gap definition is more convenient, because later on we will encounter squared roots in e.g. the non-squared energy-momentum formula (6) resp. the non-squared version of the mass gap resp. delta energy formula (9) which could not be negative (if we do not want do deal with complex numbers which is not the main focus of our research paper).

2.3 Set up of our main particle model in pure QCD without quarks and the corresponding Energy-Momentum relation

In this subchapter 2.3 we firstly want set our main particle model in pure quantum chromodynamics (QCD) without matter fields and quarks particles (2.3.1) and then model the particle interactions by using the energy-momentum relation (2.3.2) adapted to our main particle model.

2.3.1 Set up of our main particle model in pure QCD without matter fields and quarks

The main particle model in quantum chromodynamics (QCD) without matter fields and quarks particles is a single (massless) gluon travelling resp. propagating through the empty space (that is in the vacuum state) and within an color field consisting of only gluons, with positive (external) force F_{ext} . The single massless gluon could exist within the QCD framework (without quarks particles), because we assume that very high energy and temperature levels like e.g. that the gluons are residing in the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) of CERN in Geneva, Switzerland.

Then we are trying the add another massive particle (which is a hypothetical composite particle) to the single massless gluon particle in order to create a non-vacuum state from the original vacuum state (with only 1 massless gluon). But this is not possible anymore (unlike in QED and QCD with matter fields & quarks example), because the (hypothetical resp. theoretical composite) **glueball**⁹ particle can not exist in high energy enviroments but is forms only in lower energy and lower temperature levels.

Thus while in vacuum state 1 single gluon exist, in non-vacuum state, we assume that only 1 (massive) glueball is included and without any other (massless) gluons in the system. This single gluball is formed by binding with other gluons added to the system, e.g. adding 1 additional gluon to the already existing single gluon to build the single glueball (while the 2 gluons vanish in the non-vacuum state leaving only 1 single glueball behind in the system).

⁹ Even though glueballs are theoretically predicted within the QCD framework, until this day, their existence is not empirically resp. experimentally verified.

In this special case (which is a bit different than the other cases in QED and QCD with quarks) the mass gap could only potentially exist, if the energy lost from the vanishing gluon (from vacuum state) could be overcompensated by the newly forming glueball when switching von vacuum state (with 1 single gluon) to non-vacuum state (with only 1 single glueball and no other gluon because it has already disappeared in the process when the massive glueball has been formed) in our system.

2.3.2 Energy-momentum relation equation in pure QCD without quarks

Let us recall once again from formula (4) of chapter 2.1 that in the 2 particle system ($N = 2$) the total energy levels consisting of kinetic energy (i.a. depending on its momentum) and rest energy (i.a. depending on its mass) is defined as follows:

$$E_{2\text{ particles}}^{\text{Total}} = \sqrt{\left((p_1 c)^2 + (m_1 c^2)^2\right)} + \sqrt{\left((p_2 c)^2 + (m_2 c^2)^2\right)}$$

Thus the squared equation form for a system of 2 particles could be written down like this, just as formula (5) has already shown us:

$$\left(E_{2\text{ particles}}^{\text{Total}}\right)^2 = \left((p_1 c)^2 + (m_1 c^2)^2\right) + \left((p_2 c)^2 + (m_2 c^2)^2\right)$$

When applying the settings of our main particle model consisting of 1 single massless gluon and 1 massive meson (e.g. residing in a color field) the total energy level is defined as follows (As already mentioned in chapter 2.3.1, while in vacuum state there exist 1 single gluon, when switching to the non-vacuum state, the massive (hypothetical) glueball is the only particle in our system as the original massless gluon from vacuum state has vanished when forming the glueball that is only possible in lower energy levels and not in high energy enviroment like in the vacuum state with 1 single massless gluon in the system):

$$E_{\text{glueball}}^{\text{Total}} = \sqrt{\left((p_{\text{glueball}} c)^2 + (m_{\text{glueball}} c^2)^2\right)} \quad (14)$$

Therefore the squared equation form for a system of 1 single glueball could be written down like this:

$$\left(E_{glueball}^{Total}\right)^2 = \left(\left(p_{glueball} c\right)^2 + \left(m_{glueball} c^2\right)^2\right) = \left(E_{non-vacuum}^{Total}\right)^2 \quad (15)$$

Thus the squared energy levels of a single gluon (e.g. in vacuum state) that exist on in high energy enviroment is define with this formula:

$$\left(E_{gluon}^{Total}\right)^2 = \left(\left(p_{gluon} c\right)^2 + \left(m_{gluon} c^2\right)^2\right) = \left(E_{vacuum}^{Total}\right)^2 \quad (16)$$

Now we need to use the formula (9) from previous chapter 2.1 which is the mass gap definition (that is the most important formula in our piece of work) which is the energy difference between the total energy level in non-vacuum and the initial vacuum state:

$$\Delta\left(E^{Total}\right) = \left(E_{non-vacuum}^{Total}\right) - \left(E_{vacuum}^{Total}\right)$$

For convenience reasons¹⁰ we could also look at the difference between non-vacuum and the vacuum state of the squared total energy levels (which is the formula (10) from chapter 2.1) because if a mass energy gap does exist between squared energy levels, then it would also exist in normal non-squared energy levels between the vacuum and non-vacuum state:

$$\Delta\left(\left(E^{Total}\right)^2\right) = \left(E_{non-vacuum}^{Total}\right)^2 - \left(E_{vacuum}^{Total}\right)^2$$

¹⁰ Just as stated in chapter 2.1 (QED particle model) and also in 2.2 (QCD with quarks particle model), the squared version of the mass gap definition is more convenient, because later on we will encounter squared roots in e.g. the non-squared energy-momentum formula (6) resp. the non-squared version of the mass gap resp. delta energy formula (9) which could not be negative (if we do not want do deal with complex numbers which is not the key focus of our research paper).

3. Counter examples to the existence of mass gap in the Yang Mills Theory

In this crucial chapter we want to define and calculate the main conditions by applying the energy-momentum relation formula to our main particle models in quantum electrodynamics resp. QED (chapter 3.1), quantum chromodynamics resp. QCD with matter fields & quark particles (chapter 3.2) and also pure quantum chromodynamics resp. QCD with quarks (chapter 3.3).

3.1 Counter examples in QED

As we have already seen in chapter 2.1, if the initial kinetic energy (of the single photon) of the vacuum state reduces more (or exactly the same) compared to the increase of rest energy (of the electron particle) in non-vacuum state when switching from vacuum state to non-vacuum state (where massive particles like electrons exist besides e.g. the massless photons, in our case 1 photon + 1 electron), then the mass gap do not exist (in the Yang-Mills theory¹¹).

Before we present our numeric counter example to the existence of the mass gap in Yang-Mills quantum field theory which includes quantum electrodynamics (QED) as well (besides quantum chromodynamics resp. QED) that i.a. describes the interactions of charged particles like electrons or photons¹² in a electromagnetic field, we would like to present some formulas for calculating some important variables like the momentum of a single photon which is defined as follows:

11 Here we are talking about the Yang-Mills theory in broader sense which includes quantum electrodynamics (QED) where i.a. photons and electrons are modelled. Later on (chapter 3.2 and 3.3) we are using the Yang-Mills theory in a more narrow sense in the quantum chromodynamics (QCD) framework (first with matter fields and quark particles in chapter 3.2 and then without quarks in chapter 3.3).

12 In a quantum field theory, the photon is defined as a particle, wave or an excitation which is kind of like a wave.

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$$p_{\text{photon}} = p_p = \frac{h}{\lambda} \text{ with } h = \text{Planck's constant}, \lambda = \text{wavelength of photon} \quad (17)$$

$$p_p^{\text{max reasonable}} = \frac{h}{\lambda} = \frac{(6.626 * 10^{(-34)} \text{ J s})}{(10^{(-12)} \text{ m})} = \frac{\left(\frac{6.626 * 10^{(-34)} (\text{kg} * \text{m}^2)}{\text{s}} \right)}{(10^{(-12)} \text{ m})} = 6.626 * 10^{(-22)} \frac{(\text{kg} * \text{m})}{\text{s}}$$

As we could see in formula (11) above, the momentum of a photon is the Planck's constant h divided through the wavelength of the photon λ . And plug in one of the shortest type of photons, the gamma ray photons (which possess one of the highest frequencies resp. momentum/movement) one of the biggest reasonable photon momentum would be roughly $6.626 * 10^{-22} \text{ kg} * \text{m/s}$ as shown in the calculation above.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta(E^{\text{Total}})^2 &= (E_{\text{non-vacuum}}^{\text{Total}})^2 - (E_{\text{vacuum}}^{\text{Total}})^2 > 0 \text{ (condition for mass gap existence)} \\ &\rightarrow \left((p_{\text{photon}}^{\text{non-vacuum}} c)^2 + (m_{\text{photon}}^{\text{non-vacuum}} c^2)^2 \right) + \left((p_{\text{electron}}^{\text{non-vacuum}} c)^2 + (m_{\text{electron}}^{\text{non-vacuum}} c^2)^2 \right) \\ &\quad - \left((p_{\text{photon}}^{\text{vacuum}} c)^2 + (m_{\text{photon}}^{\text{vacuum}} c^2)^2 \right) > 0 \\ &\rightarrow \left(\left((p_p^{\text{nv}})^2 c^2 \right) + \left((m_p^{\text{nv}})^2 c^4 \right) \right) + \left(\left((p_e^{\text{nv}})^2 c^2 \right) + \left((m_e^{\text{nv}})^2 c^4 \right) \right) - \left(\left((p_p^{\text{v}})^2 c^2 \right) + \left((m_p^{\text{v}})^2 c^4 \right) \right) > 0 \\ &\rightarrow c^2 \left((p_p^{\text{nv}})^2 + (p_e^{\text{nv}})^2 - (p_p^{\text{v}})^2 \right) + c^4 \left((m_p^{\text{nv}})^2 + (m_e^{\text{nv}})^2 - (m_p^{\text{v}})^2 \right) > 0 \\ &\rightarrow \left((p_p^{\text{nv}})^2 + (p_e^{\text{nv}})^2 - (p_p^{\text{v}})^2 \right) + c^2 \left((m_p^{\text{nv}})^2 + (m_e^{\text{nv}})^2 - (m_p^{\text{v}})^2 \right) > 0 \\ &\rightarrow (m_e^{\text{nv}})^2 c^2 > (p_p^{\text{v}})^2, \text{ with } m_p^{\text{nv}} = m_p^{\text{v}} = 0, p_e^{\text{nv}} > 0, p_p^{\text{nv}} = 0 \text{ (pre collision) and } p_e^{\text{nv}} = p_p^{\text{nv}} = 0 \text{ (after collision)} \\ &\rightarrow (m_e^{\text{nv}})^2 > \frac{(p_p^{\text{v}})^2}{c^2} \\ &\rightarrow m_e^{\text{nv}} > \frac{p_p^{\text{v}}}{c} = \frac{\left(\frac{6.626 * 10^{(-22)} (\text{kg} * \text{m})}{\text{s}} \right)}{\left(3.000 * 10^8 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}} \right)} = 2.21 * 10^{(-30)} \text{ kg} \\ &\rightarrow \text{But in reality, } m_e \text{ is only } = 9.109 * 10^{(-31)} \text{ kg and thus } < 2.21 * 10^{(-30)} \text{ kg} \end{aligned}$$

Above we have just presented the first counter example to the mass gap existence in the Yang-Mills (quantum field) theory, with our main particle model in quantum electrodynamics (QED) describing interactions of 1 photon and 1 electron residing in an electromagnetic field exercising electromagnetic force on the single moving electron (after initial resting and then colliding with the photon moving at light speed) and completely balancing out resp. nullifying the moving electron's momentum.

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In that example, the mass of electron ($= 9.109 * 10^{-31}$ kg) is too small (resp. not $> 2.21 * 10^{-30}$ kg which need to be fulfilled) for the mass gap existence (resp. positive squared total energy difference between non-vacuum and vacuum state) to be possible.

Since the latter (counter) example is rather clear-cut, but only by assuming that after the collision of electron with the photon in non-vacuum state, both particle’s momentum would be reduced to 0 (p_{photon} goes to 0 after transforming its momentum completely to the electron initially at rest which does completely balanced out resp. nullified by the external electromagnetic force acting on the single electron), we want to assess under which conditions and circumstances the mass gap existence in our main particle model still would or would not hold.

So while we keep some of the already made assumptions in our main particle model above like positive photon momentum in vacuum state and non-vacuum state before collision and we still assume that after the collision of photon with the electron initially at rest in the non-vacuum state, the momentum of the photon is nullified resp. completely transferred to the single electron, we now assume that the momentum of the single electron may or **may not** be completely nullified resp. balanced out by the (external¹³) electromagnetic forces of the electromagnetic quantum field acting on the single electron.

13 By “external” (electromagnetic force) we are meaning that the force is relatively external compared to the “internal” subsystem consisting of only 1 photon and 1 electron particle.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta(E^{Total})^2 &= (E_{non-vacuum}^{Total})^2 - (E_{vacuum}^{Total})^2 > 0 \text{ (condition for mass gap existence)} \\ &\rightarrow \left((p_{photon}^{non-vacuum} c)^2 + (m_{photon}^{non-vacuum} c^2)^2 \right) + \left((p_{electron}^{non-vacuum} c)^2 + (m_{electron}^{non-vacuum} c^2)^2 \right) \\ &\quad - \left((p_{photon}^{vacuum} c)^2 + (m_{photon}^{vacuum} c^2)^2 \right) > 0 \\ &\rightarrow \left((p_p^{nv})^2 c^2 + (m_p^{nv})^2 c^4 \right) + \left((p_e^{nv})^2 c^2 + (m_e^{nv})^2 c^4 \right) - \left((p_p^v)^2 c^2 + (m_p^v)^2 c^4 \right) > 0 \\ &\rightarrow c^2 \left((p_p^{nv})^2 + (p_e^{nv})^2 - (p_p^v)^2 \right) + c^4 \left((m_p^{nv})^2 + (m_e^{nv})^2 - (m_p^v)^2 \right) > 0 \\ &\rightarrow \left((p_p^{nv})^2 + (p_e^{nv})^2 - (p_p^v)^2 \right) + c^2 \left((m_p^{nv})^2 + (m_e^{nv})^2 - (m_p^v)^2 \right) > 0 \\ &\rightarrow \left((p_p^{nv})^2 + (p_e^{nv})^2 - (p_p^v)^2 \right) + c^2 (m_e^{nv})^2 > 0 \text{ (with } m_p^{nv} = m_p^v = 0) \end{aligned}$$

$$\rightarrow (m_e^{nv})^2 > \frac{(p_p^v)^2 - ((p_p^{nv})^2 + (p_e^{nv})^2)}{c^2}$$

$$\rightarrow (m_e^{nv})^2 > \frac{(p_p^v)^2 - (p_e^{nv})^2}{c^2},$$

$p_p^v \geq p_e^{nv}$, $p_e^{nv} = 0$, $p_p^{nv} > 0$ (pre collision) and $p_e^{nv} \geq 0$, $p_p^{nv} = 0$ (after collision)

$$\rightarrow (m_e^{nv})^2 > \frac{(x_{min} p_p^v)^2}{c^2},$$

x_{min} = min. necessary threshold of p_{photon}^v to decrease to after collision in nv

$$\rightarrow (x_{min})^2 < \frac{(m_e^{nv})^2 (c)^2}{(p_p^v)^2}$$

$$\rightarrow x_{min} < \frac{m_e^{nv} c}{p_p^v} = \frac{(9.109 * 10^{-31} \text{ kg}) * \left(3.000 * 10^8 \frac{m}{s} \right)}{\left(6.626 * 10^{-22} \frac{kg m}{s} \right)} = 0.412421$$

$$\rightarrow m_e^{nv} > \frac{x_{min} p_p^v}{c}$$

$$\rightarrow m_e^{nv} > (?) \frac{x_{too\ big} p_p^v}{c} = \frac{0.4125 * \left(6.626 * 10^{-22} \frac{kg m}{s} \right)}{\left(3.000 * 10^8 \frac{m}{s} \right)} = 9.11075 * 10^{-31} \text{ kg}$$

$$\rightarrow m_e^{nv} = 9.109 * 10^{-31} \text{ kg} < (!) 9.11075 * 10^{-31} \text{ kg}$$

→ 2nd counter example against mass gap existence discovered!

Thus with the above calculations, we mainly want to find out $x_{\min}$ which denotes the minimum needed threshold for the initial momentum of the single photon (originally in vacuum state) to decrease to (from 1 = 100% of initial photon’s momentum) so that the existence of mass gap is still feasible when switching from vacuum to non-vacuum state by adding another single electron (initially at rest) to the whole system and then those 2 particles collide with each other, assuming that the momentum of the newly added electron in non-vacuum state may or may not be fully nullified through the (external) electromagnetic force acting on the newly added and collided electron within the electromagnetic field. And as we could see in the above calculations $x_{\min}$ need to be strictly smaller than ($<$) 0.412421 for the mass gap existence to be possible. Thus if for reasons of verification we increase the need-to-decrease-to-level of the initial momentum of the single photon $x_{\max}$ to e.g. 0.4125 (which is $>$ than the computed threshold 0.412421 that is the minimum needed amount of initial vacuum momentum decrease of the photon), then we get the result that for a mass gap to exist, the (hypothetical) mass of an electron in our main particle model (1 photon in vacuum, 1 photon + 1 electron in non-vacuum state) need to be strictly bigger than ($>$) $9.11075 * 10^{-31}$ kg that is not feasible because we know that the mass of a single electron is “only” about $9.109 * 10^{-31}$ kg which provides us with another counter example resp. a condition to generate another set of counter examples to the mass gap existence in the Yang-Mills (quantum field) theory by using our main particle model built using the theoretical framework of quantum electrodynamics (QED) and that consists of 1 photon in vacuum state and 1 photon & 1 electron residing in non-vacuum state (and all particles are residing within an electromagnetic field with external electromagnetic force acting on the single electron especially in non-vacuum state). In other words, as long as the initial momentum loss of the photon (initially in vacuum state) is not bigger than $100\% - 41.25\% = 58.75\%$, after switch from vacuum to non-vacuum state, then no mass gap could exist within the QED branch of the Yang-Mills theory¹⁴.

14 So we do not even need a 100% loss of initial photon momentum like in the 1st counter example provided above in order to proof that no mass gap could exist under certain conditions like those provided in our piece of work (e.g. that after the electron initially at rest collides with the photon, only a part of the momentum transferred from the photon to the electron need to be nullified resp. balanced out by the external electromagnetic forces of the electromagnetic field to make the existence of a mass gap impossible).

3.2 Counter examples in QCD with matter fields and quarks particles

As we have already seen in chapter 2.2, if the initial kinetic energy of the single massless gluon particle in the vacuum state reduces more (or exactly the same) compared to the increase of rest energy (of the massive meson particle) in non-vacuum state when switching from vacuum state to non-vacuum state (where massive particles like mesons - that is a quark-antiquark pair - exist besides e.g. the massless gluons, in our case 1 gluon + 1 meson in an high energy environment¹⁵), then the mass gap do not exist (in the Yang-Mills theory).

After we have presented some numerical examples against the existence of mass gap in quantum electrodynamics (QED) we want to show some counter evidence against the mass gap existence in quantum chromodynamics (QCD) with matter fields and quark particles within a quantum color field consisting of only massless gluons. We want to assess under which conditions and circumstances the mass gap existence in our main particle model still would or would not hold.

So while we keep some of the already made assumptions in our main particle model QCD with quarks in chapter 2.2 like positive gluon momentum in vacuum state¹⁶ and non-vacuum state before collision and we still assume that after the collision of the gluon with the lightest meson (which is a neutral pion) initially at rest in the non-vacuum state, the momentum of the gluon is nullified resp. completely transferred to the single meson (resp. neutral pion), we now assume that the momentum of the single meson resp. neutral pion **could not** be completely nullified resp. balanced out by the (external¹⁷) forces of the quantum color field acting on the single meson resp. neutral pion as we could see in the calculations using the energy-momentum relation equation below:

15 Because as already stated before (i.a. chapter 2.2) gluons could only exist unbounded and separately over a longer distance in a high energy & high temperature environment (which exist in the Large Hadron Collider in CERN, Switzerland).

16 We already know that gluons could only occur separately over long distance in high energy environment like in the Large Hadron Collider in CERN, Switzerland.

17 By “external” (electromagnetic force) we are meaning that the force is relatively external compared to the “internal” subsystem consisting of only 1 photon and 1 electron particle.

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$$\Delta(E^{Total})^2 = (E_{non-vacuum}^{Total})^2 - (E_{vacuum}^{Total})^2 > 0 \text{ (condition for mass gap existence)}$$

$$\rightarrow \left((p_{gluon}^{non-vacuum} c)^2 + (m_{gluon}^{non-vacuum} c^2)^2 \right) + \left((p_{meson}^{non-vacuum} c)^2 + (m_{meson}^{non-vacuum} c^2)^2 \right) - \left((p_{gluon}^{vacuum} c)^2 + (m_{gluon}^{vacuum} c^2)^2 \right) > 0$$

$$\rightarrow \left(((p_g^{nv})^2 c^2) + ((m_g^{nv})^2 c^4) \right) + \left(((p_m^{nv})^2 c^2) + ((m_m^{nv})^2 c^4) \right) - \left(((p_g^v)^2 c^2) + ((m_g^v)^2 c^4) \right) > 0$$

$$\rightarrow c^2 \left((p_g^{nv})^2 + (p_m^{nv})^2 - (p_g^v)^2 \right) + c^4 \left((m_g^{nv})^2 + (m_m^{nv})^2 - (m_g^v)^2 \right) > 0$$

$$\rightarrow \left((p_g^{nv})^2 + (p_m^{nv})^2 - (p_g^v)^2 \right) + c^2 \left((m_g^{nv})^2 + (m_m^{nv})^2 - (m_g^v)^2 \right) > 0$$

$$\rightarrow \left((p_g^{nv})^2 + (p_m^{nv})^2 - (p_g^v)^2 \right) + c^2 (m_m^{nv})^2 > 0 \text{ (with } m_g^{nv} = m_g^v = 0)$$

$$\rightarrow (m_m^{nv})^2 > \frac{(p_g^v)^2 - ((p_g^{nv})^2 + (p_m^{nv})^2)}{c^2}$$

$$\rightarrow (m_m^{nv})^2 > \frac{(p_g^v)^2 - ((p_m^{nv})^2)}{c^2},$$

$$p_g^v \geq p_m^v, p_m^{nv} = 0, p_g^{nv} > 0 \text{ (pre collision) and } p_m^{nv} > 0, p_g^{nv} = 0 \text{ (after collision)}$$

$$\rightarrow (m_m^{nv})^2 > \frac{(x_{min} p_g^v)^2}{c^2},$$

$$x_{min} = \min. \text{ necessary threshold of } p_{gluon}^v \text{ to decrease } t \text{ o after collision i n nv}$$

$$\rightarrow (x_{min})^2 < \frac{(m_m^{nv})^2 (c)^2}{(p_g^v)^2},$$

$$\text{with } p_g^v = \frac{3}{(\pi^2)} \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{p^3}{\left(e^{\left(\frac{p}{T} \right)} - 1 \right)} \right) dp = \frac{3}{(\pi^2)} \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{p^3}{\left(e^{\left(\frac{p}{(250 \text{ MeV})} \right)} - 1 \right)} \right) dp$$

$$= 2.5367 * 10^{10} \frac{\text{MeV}}{c} = 1.354 * 10^{(-11)} \frac{\text{kg} * \text{m}}{\text{s}} \text{ (average value for } p_g^v)$$

$$\rightarrow x_{min} < \frac{m_m^{nv} c}{p_g^v} = \frac{(2.40 * 10^{(-28)} \text{ kg}) * \left(3.000 * 10^8 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}} \right)}{\left(1.354 * 10^{(-11)} \frac{\text{kgm}}{\text{s}} \right)} = 5.3175775 * 10^{(-9)} \approx 0$$

$$\rightarrow m_m^{nv} > \frac{x_{min} p_g^v}{c}$$

$$\rightarrow m_m^{nv} > (?) \frac{x_{too \text{ big}} p_g^v}{c} = \frac{5.32 * 10^{(-9)} * \left(1.354 * 10^{(-11)} \frac{\text{kgm}}{\text{s}} \right)}{\left(3.000 * 10^8 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}} \right)} = 2.40109 * 10^{(-28)} \text{ kg}$$

$$\rightarrow m_m^{nv} = 2.40 * 10^{(-28)} \text{ kg} < (!) 2.40109 * 10^{(-28)} \text{ kg}$$

→ Counter example against mass gap existence discovered i n QCD with quarks !

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Thus with the above calculations where we i.a. assume that the (average) momentum of a massless gluon would be roughly $1.354 \cdot 10^{-11}$ kg* m/s (in an high energy resp. high temperature scenario like for example in the Large Hadron Collidor resp. LHC), we mainly want to find out $x_{\min}$ which denotes the minimum needed threshold for the initial momentum of the single gluon (originally in vacuum state) to decrease to (from 1 = 100% of initial massless gluons’s momentum) so that the existence of mass gap is still feasible when switching from vacuum to non-vacuum state by adding another single massive meson (initially at rest) to the whole system (we will add the **lightest meson** that is the **neutral pion** which is not charged) and then those 2 particles collide with each other, assuming that the momentum of the newly added massive meson (neutral pion) in non-vacuum state could not be fully but only partially nullified through the (external) force acting on the newly added and collided meson within the color field in QCD with quarks. And as we could see in the above calculations $x_{\min}$ need to be strictly smaller than ($<$) $5.3175775 \cdot 10^{-9}$ (which is approximately 0) for the mass gap existence to be possible. Thus if for reasons of verification we increase the need-to-decrease-to-level of the initial momentum of the single gluon $x_{\max}$ to e.g. $5.32 \cdot 10^{-9}$ (which is $>$ than the computed threshold $5.3175775 \cdot 10^{-9}$ that is the minimum needed amount of initial vacuum momentum decrease of the gluon), then we get the result that for a mass gap to exist, the (hypothetical) mass of a meson in our main particle model (1 gluon in vacuum, 1 gluon + 1 meson in non-vacuum state) need to be strictly bigger than ($>$) $2.48233 \cdot 10^{-28}$ kg that is not feasible because we know that the mass of a single (lightest) meson resp. neutral pion is “only” about $2.40 \cdot 10^{-28}$ kg which provides us with another counter example resp. a condition to generate another set of counter examples to the mass gap existence in the Yang-Mills (quantum field) theory by using our main particle model built using the theoretical framework of quantum chromodynamics (QCD) including matter fields & quarks and that consists of 1 gluon in vacuum state and 1 gluon & 1 meson (resp. neutral pion which is the lightest meson) residing in non-vacuum state (and all particles are residing within a color field with external force acting on the single meson especially in non-vacuum state). In other words, as long as the initial momentum loss of the gluon (initially in vacuum state) is not bigger than $1 - 5.3175775 \cdot 10^{-9} = \text{almost } 1 = \text{almost } 100\%$ (which is not really possible in QCD where momentum loss of 50% or (a lot) less are more realistic and feasible), after switch from vacuum to non-vacuum state, then no mass gap could exist within the QCD branch (incl. quark particles) of the Yang-Mills theory.

3.3 Counter examples and irregularities in pure QCD without quarks particles

In this subchapter 3.3 after we have shown that the mass gap does not exist under certain rather realistic scenarios in both the quantum electrodynamics (QED) and quantum chromodynamics (QCD) with quarks, now we want to show that there exist also counter examples and irregularities in pure QCD without any matter fields and quarks particles.

3.3.1 Irregularities in pure QCD

When in case a) the hypothetical resp. theoretical glueballs (with mass > 0) - for which no unambiguous experimental evidence could be found - do not really exist: then non-vacuum state could never exist in pure QCD with only the massless gluons occurring, This means that no mass gap resp. no energy difference between vacuum and non-vacuum state could be calculated.

In case b) when hypothetical resp. theoretical glueballs (with mass > 0) do exist now, but we want to add them separately to the separate gluons simultaneously (to fit into our main particle model shown in chapter 2.1 for QED and chapter 2.2 for QCD with quarks (extreme high energy situation), then this would be not possible, because while gluons could only exist in high energy situations, glueballs are only expected to occur in lower energy (and temperature) spectrum, so the non-vacuum state could not exist with 1 gluon and 1 massive glueball separately. Which in this case would make the calculation of mass gap impossible

Only in case c) where we need to adjust the main particle model (unlike in QED and QCD with quarks), the mass gap could theoretically be defined and calculated. Where this mass gap always exist under all and generic conditions need to be assessed in the next sub chapter 3.3.2.

3.3.2 Counter examples in pure QCD without quark particles

We have already seen in chapter 2.3, that if the initial kinetic energy of the single massless gluon particle in the vacuum state reduces more (or exactly the same) compared to the increase of rest energy of the massive (hypothetical) glueball particle in non-vacuum state when switching from vacuum state to non-vacuum state which is only possible if the energy lost from the vanishing gluon (from vacuum state) could be overcompensated by the newly forming glueball when switching von vacuum state (with 1 single gluon) to non-vacuum state in our system (with only 1 single glueball and no other gluon there because it has already disappeared in the process when the massive glueball has been formed), then the mass gap do not exist (in the Yang-Mills theory).

After we have presented some numerical examples against the existence of mass gap in quantum electrodynamics (QED) and quantum chromodynamics with quarks we want to show some counter evidence gainst the mass gap existence in quantum chromodynamics (QCD) without matter fields and quark particles (but with the hypothetical massive glueball particles) whithin a quantum color field consisting of only massless gluons. We want to assess under which conditions and circumstances the mass gap existence in our main particle model still would or would not hold.

Thus while we keep some of the already made assumptions in our main particle model QCD without quarks in chapter 2.3 like postive gluon momentum in vacuum state¹⁸ we assume that this single massless gluon in vacuum state would be combined with another added gluon to our main particle system (cf. Chapter 2.3) and will form another massive particle which is the hypothetical single glueball particle in the non-vacuum state (while the the massless gluons are both vanishing resp. merging into the newly build glueball particle) as we could see in the calculations using the energy-momentum relation equation below:

¹⁸ We already know that gluons could only occur separately over long distance in high energy enviroment like in the Large Hadron Collider in CERN, Switzerland.

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$$\Delta(E^{Total})^2 = (E_{non-vacuum}^{Total})^2 - (E_{vacuum}^{Total})^2 > 0 \text{ (condition for mass gap existence)}$$

$$\rightarrow \left((p_{gluon}^{non-vacuum} c)^2 + (m_{gluon}^{non-vacuum} c^2)^2 \right) + \left((p_{glueball}^{non-vacuum} c)^2 + (m_{glueball}^{non-vacuum} c^2)^2 \right) - \left((p_{gluon}^{vacuum} c)^2 + (m_{gluon}^{vacuum} c^2)^2 \right) > 0$$

$$\rightarrow \left((p_g^{nv})^2 c^2 + (m_g^{nv})^2 c^4 \right) + \left((p_{gb}^{nv})^2 c^2 + (m_{gb}^{nv})^2 c^4 \right) - \left((p_g^v)^2 c^2 + (m_g^v)^2 c^4 \right) > 0$$

$$\rightarrow c^2 \left((p_g^{nv})^2 + (p_{gb}^{nv})^2 - (p_g^v)^2 \right) + c^4 \left((m_g^{nv})^2 + (m_{gb}^{nv})^2 - (m_g^v)^2 \right) > 0$$

$$\rightarrow \left((p_g^{nv})^2 + (p_{gb}^{nv})^2 - (p_g^v)^2 \right) + c^2 \left((m_g^{nv})^2 + (m_{gb}^{nv})^2 - (m_g^v)^2 \right) > 0$$

$$\rightarrow \left((p_g^{nv})^2 + (p_{gb}^{nv})^2 - (p_g^v)^2 \right) + c^2 (m_{gb}^{nv})^2 > 0 \text{ (with } m_g^{nv} = m_g^v = 0)$$

$$\rightarrow (m_{gb}^{nv})^2 > \frac{(p_g^v)^2 - ((p_g^{nv})^2 + (p_{gb}^{nv})^2)}{c^2}$$

$$\rightarrow (m_{gb}^{nv})^2 > \frac{(p_g^v)^2 - ((p_g^{nv})^2)}{c^2},$$

$$p_g^v > 0, p_g^{nv} > 0 \text{ (pre merge) and } p_{gb}^{nv} > 0, p_g^{nv} = 0 \text{ (after merge)}$$

$$\rightarrow (m_{gb}^{nv})^2 > \frac{(x_{min} p_g^v)^2}{c^2},$$

x_{min} = min. necessary threshold of p_{gluon}^v to decrease to after switching from v to nv

$$\rightarrow (x_{min})^2 < \frac{(m_{gb}^{nv})^2 (c)^2}{(p_g^v)^2},$$

$$\text{with } p_g^v = \frac{3}{(\pi^2)} \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{p^3}{\left(e^{\left(\frac{p}{T} \right)} - 1 \right)} \right) dp = \frac{3}{(\pi^2)} \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{p^3}{\left(e^{\left(\frac{p}{(250 \text{ MeV})} \right)} - 1 \right)} \right) dp$$

$$= 2.5367 * 10^{10} \frac{\text{MeV}}{c} = 1.354 * 10^{(-11)} \frac{\text{kg} * \text{m}}{\text{s}} \text{ (average value for } p_g^v)$$

$$\rightarrow x_{min} < \frac{m_{gb}^{nv} c}{p_g^v} = \frac{(2.6745 * 10^{(-27)} \text{ kg}) * \left(3.000 * 10^8 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}} \right)}{\left(1.354 * 10^{(-11)} \frac{(\text{kg m})}{\text{s}} \right)} = 5.925775 * 10^{(-8)} \approx 0$$

$$\rightarrow m_{gb}^{nv} > \frac{x_{min} p_g^v}{c}$$

$$\rightarrow m_{gb}^{nv} > (?) \frac{x_{too \text{ big}} p_g^v}{c} = \frac{5.93 * 10^{(-8)} * \left((1.354) 10^{(-11)} \frac{(\text{kg m})}{\text{s}} \right)}{\left(3.000 * 10^8 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}} \right)} = 2.6764 * 10^{(-27)} \text{ kg}$$

$$\rightarrow m_{gb}^{nv} = 2.6745 * 10^{(-27)} \text{ kg} < (!) 2.6764 * 10^{(-27)} \text{ kg}$$

→ Counter example against mass gap existence found in pure QCD without quarks!

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Thus with the above calculations where we i.a. assume that the (average) momentum of a massless gluon would be about $1.354 \cdot 10^{-11}$ kg* m/s (in an high energy resp. high temperature scenario like for example in the Large Hadron Collider resp. LHC), we mainly want to find out $x_{\min}$ which denotes the minimum needed threshold for the initial momentum of the single gluon (originally in vacuum state) to decrease to (from 1 = 100% of initial massless gluons’s momentum) so that the existence of mass gap is still feasible when switching from vacuum to non-vacuum state by merging the existing single gluon from the vacuum state with another added gluon to form the massive hypothetical glueball particle whose existence is only predicted in theoretical models and (lattice QED) simulations. For our calculations, we take the lightest possible glueball into our model with is predicted to have the approximate mass of about $2.6745 \cdot 10^{-27}$ kg ¹⁹.

19 Glueballs are expected to obtain masses around 10^{-27} kg, 10^{-26} kg and even 10^{-25} kg but it could never be heavier or even as heavy as $3.951 \cdot 10^{-25}$ kg which is about the mass of the heaviest whole atom, the uranium-238 atom. Even if we would (unrealistically) assume that the mass of the hypothetical glueball would be as heavy as the heaviest whole (uranium-238) atom ($3.951 \cdot 10^{-25}$ kg), the minimum needed threshold for the initial momentum of the single gluon (originally in vacuum state) to decrease to which is $x_{\min}$ would still only be $8.75406 \cdot 10^{-6}$ that is still almost 0 which means that $1 - x_{\min} = 1 - 8.75406 \cdot 10^{-6}$ would still be almost 1 which is almost 100% which means the loss of initial momentum of the gluon in vacuum after switching to non-vacuum state (and forming the massive glueball from gluons) would at least need to be almost 100% for the existence of mass gap to be possible which is not really feasible in quantum chromodynamics (QCD) framework with strong forces and complex interactions between the particles occurring in the whole system (and even if 100% loss of initial momentum of the massless gluon originally in vacuum state would be possible, it would not be a very likely scenario and the other more likely situations with loss of initial momentum of 50% or even less for the gluon would provide a set of counter examples to the mass gap existence in pure quantum chromodynamics resp. QCD). And to go to the other direction, if the mass of glueballs would (hypothetically) be lower than the current lower bound $2.6745 \cdot 10^{-27}$ kg (which is not expected to be the case from theoretical predictions), $x_{\min}$ which is the minimum needed threshold for the initial momentum of the single gluon (originally in vacuum state) to decrease to for the mass gap existence to be possible (in pure QCD here) would get even smaller (even $<$ than $5.925775 \cdot 10^{-8}$) with a hypothetically increasing mass of the glueball and thus making the minimum needed loss of the initial momentum of the gluon in vacuum state ($= 1 - x_{\min}$) for mass gap existence to be feasible go even nearer to 1 resp. 100% which is even more unlikely to happen because as already elaborated many times before, the loss of initial momentum of the original gluon particle in (pure or non-pure) quantum chromodynamics resp. QCD is not even near 100% on average but it is expected to only be around 50% or even less than this threshold.

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And plug in i.a. this (lightest possible) mass of gluon we could see in the above calculations that $x_{\min}$ need to be strictly smaller than ($<$) $5.925775 * 10^{-8}$ (which is approximately 0 as well like in QCD with quarks example) for the mass gap existence to be possible. Thus if for reasons of verification we increase the need-to-decrease-to-level of the initial momentum of the single gluon $x_{\max}$ to e.g. $5.93 * 10^{-8}$ (which is $>$ than the calculated threshold $5.925775 * 10^{-9}$ that is the minimum needed amount of decrease of the initial vacuum momentum of the gluon), then we get the result that for a mass gap to exist, the (hypothetical) mass of a glueball in our main particle model (1 gluon in vacuum, 1 glueball in non-vacuum state) need to be strictly bigger than ($>$) $2.6764 * 10^{-27}$ kg that is not feasible because we know that the mass of a single (lightest) meson resp. neutral pion is “only” about $2.6745 * 10^{-27}$ kg.

This provides us with another counter example resp. a condition to generate another set of counter examples to the mass gap existence in the Yang-Mills (quantum field) theory by using our main particle model built using the theoretical framework of pure quantum chromodynamics (QCD) without matter fields & quarks and our main particle model consists of 1 gluon in vacuum state and 1 glueball (in its lightest possible mass) residing in non-vacuum state (and all particles are residing within a color field with external force acting on the single glueball especially in non-vacuum state).

In other words, as long as the initial momentum loss of the gluon (initially in vacuum state) is not bigger than $1 - 5.925775 * 10^{-8} = \text{almost } 1 = \text{almost } 100\%$ (which is not really possible in QCD where only momentum losses of 50% or (a lot) less are more realistic and feasible²⁰), after switch from vacuum to non-vacuum state, then no mass gap could exist within the pure quantum chromodynamics resp. pure QCD branch (without matter fields & quark particles) of the Yang-Mills theory.

20 Even if a 100% momentum loss would be possible (e.g. when the momentum of the massive particle in non-vacuum state of the system is balanced by an external force acting on the massive particle), it is more likely that situations occur in which the momentum loss is by far less than 100 % like e.g. only 50% or even less which would provide counter examples to the existence of mass gap in both pure quantum electrodynamics (QED) without quarks (this subchapter 3.3) and with quarks (subchapter 3.2) as well (besides the already discovered conditions and set of counter examples for quantum electrodynamics resp. QED which is not the main focus in our research paper and also for the academic research community).

4. Conclusion

The Yang-Mills Theory’s existence and mass gap problem is one of the unsolved problems in mathematics and mathematical physics. The main focus of this research paper is to try to verify whether there exist a mass gap in the Yang Mills theory that is a quantum field theory including both quantum chromodynamics (QCD) and quantum electrodynamicis (QED). Especially the proof of mass gap existence in non-gauge theories like (pure) quantum electrodynamicis (QED) without quark particles is of high academical interest.

Although the academical literature expects that the mass gap should exist in non-abelian gauge theories (which especially includes quantum chromodynamics resp. QCD) in any dimensions less or equal than 4²¹, up to this day, no unconditional resp. generic proof (valid for all dimensions, circumstances and use cases) could be delivered for the mass gap existence even in those non-abelian gauge theories like quantum chromodynamics resp. QCD²².

For the analysis, we have built our main particle model first using the quantum electrodynamicis (QED) framework (chapter 2.1) and then we utilize the quantum chromodynamics (QCD) with matter fields & quark particles (chapter 2.2) and lastly the pure QCD without quarks particles (chapter 2.3) for our new assessment of the mass gap existence in the Yang-Mills theory.

21 cf. i.a. Farakos, K., Koutsoumbas, G. & Sarantakos, S. (1987) and Modal (2023)

22 As stated before, Modal (2023) tried a new geometrical approach and proved the map gap existence under some specific conditions (e.g. positive sign of corresponding regularized Bakry-Émery Ricci curvature) in the non-abelian renormalized Yang-Mills theory (which is a renormalized resp. extended version of the non-abelian Yang-Mills theory) and restricting the domain of analysis to less than 5 real coordinates dimensions resp. especially to the 4th and 3rd dimensional real coordinates space.

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The main focus of this research paper was resp. is to show under which generic conditions and circumstances the mass gap could possibly exist (and if there exist irregularities or counter examples to the mass gap existence) for use cases in quantum electrodynamics (QED), quantum chromodynamics (QCD) with matter fields & quarks and finally in pure QCD without quark particles ²³.

After conducting our main analysis, we have come to conclusion that no mass gap could always and unconditionally be found under certain realistic conditions (concerning the relationship of minimum required initial momentum decrease of the massless vacuum particle and mass of the added resp. formed particle in non-vacuum state) no matter if the theoretical framework includes abelian gauge theories like quantum electrodynamics (QED) or non-abelian, non-pure gauge theories like quantum chromodynamics (QCD) with matter fields & quark particles or non-abelian pure gauge theories like QCD with quarks.

²³ As already stated in chapter 1, for completeness reasons and for better demonstrating our analytical approach with our newly built main particle model, we will try to find conditions of mass gap existence in quantum electrodynamics (QED) which unlike non-abelian gauge theories like quantum chromodynamics (with quarks or pure QCD without quarks) is not of main interest of the academic community but it (QED, an abelian gauge theory) is still included in the Yang-Mills quantum field theory in the broader sense.

References

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